

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXXAMINATION – APRIL-MAY 2021
RGN 23, RM 18 & PBM 4 HEALTH INFORMATICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Paa Ekow is a new staff nurse who has been employed into your facility with no knowledge in Health Information Management Systems. As a nursing/midwifery student who has been introduced to health informatics help him on the following:

- a. i. List **Three** main characteristics of Health Information Management System - 3marks
- ii. Explain the characteristics stated in **(1a)** - 3marks
- b. i. State Any **Three** Important Features of Health Information Management System - 3marks
- ii. Give **Three** examples of static and dynamic information - 3marks
- c. Outline **Three** advantages and **Two** disadvantages of Health Information Management System- 5marks
- d. Mention **Three** importance of keeping records at the hospital - 1½marks
- e. Outline **Three** ethical use of patients information - 1½marks

BEFORE YOU LEARN TO CARE
YOU MUST CARE TO LEARN.

Please Turn Over

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Nana Aba wants to buy some computer hardware from your shop. As a nursing/midwifery student assist her on:

a. Outline **Two** function of the following :

- i. Motherboard - 1mark
- ii. Central Processing Unit (CPU) - 1mark

b. Give Four (4) difference Read Only Memory (ROM) and Random Access memory (RAM) - 4marks

c. Identify and explain the parts of the mouse labeled - 4¹/₂marks

d. Explain the function of computer keyboard - 1mark

ii. List **Any Four** parts the computer keyboard - 2marks

e. Discuss **Any One** categories/groups of computer hardware - 3¹/₂marks

f. Differentiate between system and application software - 3marks

NMTC/BEREKUM / ST. MARY'S CAMPUS- DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER 2016
NMI 111 NURSING AND MIDWIFERY INFORMATICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

Instructions:

- Answer all questions,
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question one

- a. Define the following terms:
- i. Health Informatics -
 - ii. Bugs - 1 ½ mark
 - iii. Drive - 1 ½ mark
 - iv. Compatibility - 1 ½ mark
 - v. Booting -
- b. State and explain THREE benefits of Health Informatics to a nurse/midwife - 6marks
- c. Mention any TWO (2) barriers in adopting Health Informatics - 1mark
- d. Differentiate between the following terms:
- i. Information and Data - 2marks
 - ii. Super and Minicomputers - 2marks
- e. State the three people involve in health informatics - 1½ mark

Question Two

- a. Explain the following terms
- i. System Software - 2marks
 - ii. Utility program - 2marks
 - iii. Open Source software - 2marks
 - iv. Packaged/Off-the shelf software - 2marks
- b. Draw and label the components of a computer system - 6marks
- c. List **FOUR** function of the operating system - 2 marks
- d. State and explain **TWO** advantages and disadvantages of computers - 4marks

Question Three

a.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1						
2	RECORDS OF PATIENT AT HOLY FAMILY HOSPITAL, BEREKUM					
3	Name of Patient	Pulse(bm)	Temp()	Respiration (cmb)		
4	Kumi Priscilla	72	32	15		
5	Kuuri-Naa Joycelyn	82	35	17		
6	Nkamaa Gloria	82	28	19		
7	Nketiah Fosua Elizabeth	76	30	18		
8	Ntiamoah Sarah Marfo	71	31.5	18.5		
9	Nuamah Gifty Dapaah	70	36	16		
10	Nuamah Konadu Freda	73	33	14		
11	Nyantakiwaa Linda	75	31	13.5		
12						
13						
14	Use the diagram to state the functions for question (i) -(iv)					
15		i. Sum up the data in cell B4 –B11. (2marks)				
16		ii. Find the highest/max in cell C4 – C11 (2marks)				
17		iii. Multiple the data in cell D9 and D10 (2marks)				
18		iv. Divide the minimum data in cell D4 and D12 by 2 (2marks)				

b. Write the fullnames of the following abbreviations

- i. HIPAA - 1mark
- ii. HI - 1mark
- iii. HER - 1mark
- iv. ABC - 1mark
- v. ATM - 1mark

c. Explain the following the terms:

- a) Hacking and plagiarism - 2marks
- b) Confidentiality and privacy - 2marks

d. Mention Three advantages and disadvantages of the Internet - 3marks

HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE, BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION
PBMI HEALTH INFORMATICS
ALLOWED TIME : (1 1/2 HOURS)

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One (1)

1) Explain the following terms:

- a) Bug (1/2 mark)
- b) Compatibility (1 mark)
- c) Driver (1/2 mark)

2) List the **TWO** types of computers according to their purpose (2 marks)

3) Draw the processing cycle of a computer (3 marks)

4) State and explain **TWO** advantages of the usage of computer to nurse/midwife (2 marks)

5) State **THREE** disadvantages of the usage of computer to nurse/midwife (1 1/2 marks)

6) Identify the following symbols and give out their functions (6 marks)

- a)

7) List **SIX** medical fields that need informatics to improve their work (3 marks)

Question Two(2)

1) Define the following terms:

- a) Health Informatics (1/2 mark)
- b) Information (1/2 mark)
- c) Data (1/2 mark)

2) State and explain the **TWO** types of **DATA** and **INFORMATION** (3 marks)

3) State the **THREE** things that form Health informatics (1 1/2 marks)

4) Evaluate the **THREE** types of the software (3 marks)

5) List **FOUR** functions of the operating system (2 marks)

6) Differentiate the following terms with examples:

- a) Hardware (1 1/2 marks)
- b) Software (1 1/2 marks)
- c) Communication Devices (1 1/2 marks)

- 7) State the FOUR features on **WINDOWS DESKTOP** (2marks)
- 8) List the **DEVICES** of the following : (1mark)
- a) Four (Input Devices) (1mark)
 - b) Four (Output Devices) (1mark)
 - c) Two (Storage Devices) (1/2 mark)

Question Three (3)

1. Outline **FOUR (4)** features of Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word (4marks)
2. Write down the shortcut for the following commands (1mark)
- a) Save (1mark)
 - b) Print (1mark)
 - c) Cut (1mark)
 - d) Copy (1mark)
 - e) Paste (1mark)
3. Outline **TWO PRIVACY PRINCIPLES** in nursing (2marks)
4. List **ANY FOUR** search engines (2marks)
5. List **ANY FOUR** uses of internet to a midwife (2marks)

H13							
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	HOLY FAMILY NURSING & MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE, BEREKUM						
2	END OF SEMESTER GRADING SHEET						
3							
4	FIRST NAME	SECOND NAME	FULL NAME	ANATOMY	INFORMATICS	INFECTION PREV.	
5	Nyameye	Aba		58	87	77	
6	Samuel	Kojo		68	65	68	
7	Erica	Bohema		79	72	84	
8	Maama	Yaa		92	69	79	
9	Kwabena	Theophilus		85	87	68	
10							
11							
12							

- 6a) Concatenate the full names of "Samuel Kojo" and "Erica Bohema" in cell "C" with a formula (2marks)
- b) Sum up "Nyameye Aba's" total marks on "Informatics" with a formula (1mark)
- c) Divide "Nyameye Aba's" total marks on "Informatics" by TWO (2) with a formula (1mark)

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM./ST. MARY CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2017

RGN 20/RM15/PBM1 (NMI 111) NURSING & MIDWIFERY INFORMATICS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One (1)

- 1) Explain the following terms:
 - a) Bug (½ mark)
 - b) Compatibility (½ mark)
 - c) Driver (½ mark)
- 2) List the **FOUR** types of digital computers (2marks)
- 3) Draw the anatomy of the computer (3marks)
- 4) State and explain **TWO** advantages of the usage of computer to nurse/midwife (2marks)
- 5) State **THREE** disadvantages of the usage of computer to nurse/midwife (1½ marks)
- 6) Describe **FIVE** features of Microsoft Excel to Microsoft Word (5marks)
- 7) Explain the functions of the following:
 - a) Title bar (1 mark)
 - b) Function bar (1mark)
 - c) Menu bar (1 mark)
 - D) Task bar (1mark)
 - d) Restore button (1mark)

Question Two (2)

1. Defined the following terms:
 - a) Health Informatics (½ mark)
 - b) Information (½ mark)
 - c) Data (½ mark)
2. State and explain the **TWO** types of **DATA** and **INFORMATION** (3marks)
3. State the **THREE** things that forms Health informatics (1½ marks)
4. Evaluate the **THREE** types of the software (3marks)

5. List **FOUR** functions of the operating system (2marks)
6. Explain the following application software:
 - a) Packaged/ Off-the-shelf software (1½ marks)
 - b) Customized software (1½ marks)
 - c) Open source software (1½ marks)
7. Give **TWO** classification of **ROM** and **RAM** (2marks)
8. List the **DEVICES** of the Following:
 - a) Four **INPUT DEVICES** (1mark)
 - b) **FOUR OUTPUT DEVICES** (1mark)
 - c) **TWO COMMUNICATION DEVICES** (1mark)

Question Three (3)

1. Draw **RING TOPOLOGIES** and give out **ONE** advantage and disadvantage of it (4marks)
2. Write down the shortcut for the following commands
 - a) Save (1mark)
 - b) Print (1mark)
 - c) Cut (1mark)
 - d) Copy (1mark)
 - e) Paste (1mark)
3. Differentiate between a Local Network and Metropolitan Area Network (4marks)
4. List **TWO** reasons for using a **Local Area Network** (2marks)
5. Outline **TWO PRIVACY PRINCIPLES** in nursing (2marks)
6. List **ANY FOUR** search engines (2marks)
- 7) Identify the following symbols and give out their functions (1marks)
 - a) (1mark)
 - b) (1mark)